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Arithmetic Sequential Graceful Labeling on Star Related Graphs

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Abstract

Objectives: To identify a new family of Arithmetic sequential graceful graphs.

Methods: The methodology involves mathematical formulation for labeling of the vertices of a given graph and subsequently establishing that these formulations give rise to arithmetic sequential graceful labeling. **Findings:** In this study, we analyzed some star related graphs namely Star graph, U-star, t-star, and double star proved that these graphs possess Arithmetic sequential graceful labeling. **Novelty:** Here, we introduced a new labeling called Arithmetic sequential graceful labeling and we give Arithmetic sequential graceful labeling to some star related graphs.

Keywords: Star graph; t-star; U-star; Graceful labeling; Double star

1 Introduction

Graph labeling is one of the most exciting areas of research in graph theory. Labeling is the process of giving values to edges or vertices. According to a recent dynamic survey,⁽¹⁾ of graph labeling, numerous scholars contribute their work on various forms of graceful labeling, such as Skolem Graceful Labeling⁽²⁾, Edge Even Graceful Labeling^(3,4). Odd Graceful Labeling⁽⁵⁾, and so on. Motivated by the idea of graceful labeling, we developed arithmetic sequential graceful labeling as an injective function of a simple, finite, connected, undirected, and non-trivial graph G as an injective function $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{a, a + d, a + 2d, a + 3d, \dots, 2(a + qd)\}$ where $a \geq 0$ and $d \geq 1$ such that for each edge $uv \in E(G)$ $f^* : E(G) \rightarrow \{d, 2d, 3d, 4d, \dots, qd\}$ defined by $f^*(uv) = |f(u) - f(v)|$ is a bijective. Also, we proved some star related graphs are arithmetic sequential graceful.

Definition 1.1: A star graph is the complete bipartite graph $K_{1,n}$, a tree with one internal node and n leaves.

Definition 1.2: For t number of star graphs, $t \geq 2$ namely $K_{1,n_1}, K_{1,n_2}, \dots, K_{1,n_t}$ then the t -star graph is constructed by joining the apex vertices of each K_{1,n_i} and $K_{1,n_{i+1}}$ to vertices $u_i : 1 \leq i \leq t - 1, n_i \geq 1$.

Definition 1.3: A U-star graph is formed by linking the leaves of two star graphs by a bridge.

Definition 1.4: The double star graph is created by linking the centers of 2 star graphs, $K_{1,n}$ and $K_{1,m}$, with an edge.

2 Methodology

A simple, finite, connected, undirected, non-trivial graph G is arithmetic sequential graceful graph, if the function $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{a, a + d, a + 2d, a + 3d, \dots, 2(a + qd)\}$ where $a \geq 0$ and $d \geq 1$ is an injective function and for each edge $uv \in E(G)$, the induced function $f^* : E(G) \rightarrow \{d, 2d, 3d, 4d, \dots, qd\}$ defined by $f^*(uv) = |f(u) - f(v)|$ is a bijective. The function, then the graph G is called arithmetic sequential graceful graph.

3 Results and Discussion

Theorem 3.1:

The graph $K_{1, n}, n \geq 1$ admits arithmetic sequential graceful labeling.

Proof: Consider the graph $G = K_{1, n}, n \geq 1$

Let $V(G) = \{v_0\} \cup \{v_i: 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ and

$E(G) = \{v_0v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$

Here $|V| = n + 1, (E) = n$.

We define a function $f : V \rightarrow \{a, a + d, a + 2d, a + 3d, \dots, 2(a + qd)\}$

The vertex labelings are as follows,

$$f(v_0) = a + nd$$

$$f(v_i) = a + (i - 1)d, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n$$

From the function $f^* : E(G) \rightarrow \{d, 2d, 3d, 4d, \dots, qd\}$, we get the edge labels of the graph $K_{1, n}, n \geq 1$ as follows

Table 1. Edge labels of the graph $K_{1, n}, n \geq 1$

Nature of n	$n \geq 1$
$f^*(v_0v_i)$	$ (n - i + 1)d , 1 \leq i \leq n$

The function f is clearly injective and also Table 1 shows that

$f^* : E \rightarrow \{d, 2d, 3d, 4d, \dots, qd\}$ is bijective. Hence f is arithmetic sequential graceful labeling and the graph $K_{1, n}$ is arithmetic sequential graceful graph.

Example 3.1.1:

The Star graph admits arithmetic sequential graceful labeling.

Theorem 3.2:

The double star admits arithmetic sequential graceful graph for $n, m \geq 1$.

Proof:

Let G be a double star. $V(G) = \{v_0, u_0\} \cup \{v_i: 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{u_i: 1 \leq i \leq m\}$ and

$E(G) = \{v_0u_0\} \cup \{v_0v_i: 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup$

$$\{u_0 u_i : 1 \leq i \leq m\}$$

Here $|V| = n + m + 2, |E| = n + m + 1$

Define the function $f : V \rightarrow \{a, a + d, a + 2d, a + 3d, \dots, 2(a + qd)\}$

The vertex labelings are as follows,

$$f(v_i) = a + (i - 1)d, 1 \leq i \leq n$$

$$f(u_i) = a + (n + i)d, 1 \leq i \leq m$$

$$f(v_0) = a + (n + m + 1)d$$

$$f(u_0) = a + nd$$

Table 2. Edge labels of the double star, $n, m \geq 1$.

Nature of n, m	$n, m \geq 1$
$f^*(u_0 v_0)$	$ (m + 1)d $
$f^*(v_0 v_i)$	$ (n + m + 2 - i)d , 1 \leq i \leq n$
$f^*(u_0 u_i)$	$ id , 1 \leq i \leq n$

The function f is clearly injective and also table 2 shows that $f^* : E \rightarrow \{d, 2d, 3d, 4d, \dots, qd\}$ is bijective. Hence f is arithmetic sequential graceful labeling and the graph double star is arithmetic sequential graceful graph.

Example 3.2.1:

The double star graph admits arithmetic sequential graceful graphs.

Theorem 3.3:

The graph t - star, $t \geq 2$ admits arithmetic sequential graceful labeling.

Proof: Let G be a t - star, $t \geq 2$ graph.

Let $V(G) = \{v_i : 1 \leq i \leq m\} \cup$

$\{u_j : 1 \leq j \leq m - 1\} \cup \{v_{jk} : 1 \leq i \leq m; 1 \leq k \leq n_j\}$ and $E(G) = \{v_j v_{jk} : 1 \leq j \leq m; 1 \leq k \leq n_j\} \cup \{v_i u_i : 1 \leq i \leq m - 1\} \cup$

$\{u_{i v_{i+1}} : 1 \leq i \leq m - 1\}$

Here $|V| = \sum_{i=1}^m n_{i+2m-1}$,

$$|E| = \sum_{i=1}^m n_{i+2m-2}$$

Define a function $f : V \rightarrow \{a, a + d, a + 2d, a + 3d, \dots, 2(a + qd)\}$

The vertex labelings are as follows,

$$f(v_i) = a + (m - i)d, 1 \leq i \leq m$$

$$f(u_j) = a + \left\lceil \sum_{i=1}^j n_i + j + m - 1 \right\rceil, 1 \leq j \leq m - 1$$

$$f(v_{1k}) = a + ([m + k] - 1)d, 1 \leq k \leq n_1$$

For $2 \leq j \leq m$,

$$f(v_{jk}) = a + \left\lceil \sum_{i=1}^{j-1} n_{i+j+m-2+k} \right\rceil d, 1 \leq k \leq n_j$$

From the function

$f^* : E(G) \rightarrow \{d, 2d, 3d, 4d, \dots, qd\}$, we get the edge labels of the graph t -star, $t \geq 2$ as follows

Table 3. Edge labels of the t -star, $t \geq 2$

Nature of n	$n \geq 1$
$f^*(v_i u_j)$	$\left\lceil [(m - i) - (\sum_{i=1}^j n_{i+j+m-1})] d \right\rceil, 1 \leq i \leq m, 1 \leq j \leq m - 1$
$f^*(v_i v_{1k})$	$\lceil (-i - k + 1)d \rceil, 1 \leq i \leq m, 1 \leq k \leq n_1$
$f^*(v_i v_{jk})$	$\left\lceil [(m - i) - (\sum_{i=1}^{j-1} n_{i+j+m-2+k})] d \right\rceil, 1 \leq i \leq m, 1 \leq k \leq n_j$

The function f is clearly injective and also table 3 shows that $f^* : E \rightarrow \{d, 2d, 3d, 4d, \dots, qd\}$ is bijective. Hence f is arithmetic sequential graceful labeling and the graph t -star is arithmetic sequential graceful graph.

Example 3.3.1:

3 - star graph admits arithmetic sequential graceful labeling.

Theorem 3.4:

The U -star graph admits arithmetic sequential graceful labeling, for $n \geq 1, n \in N$.

Proof: Let G be a U -star graph. $V(G) = (w_1) \cup (w_2) \cup (v_0) \cup (u_0) \cup \{v_{i:1 \leq i \leq n}\} \cup \{u_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ and $E(G) = \{w_1 v_0, v_0 u_0, w_2 u_0\} \cup \{w_1 v_{i:1 \leq i \leq n}\} \cup \{w_2 u_{i:1 \leq i \leq n}\}$

Here $|V| = 2n + 4, |E| = 2n + 3$

Define the function $f : V \rightarrow \{a, a + d, a + 2d, a + 3d, \dots, 2(a + qd)\}$

The vertex labelings are as follows,

Case (i): when $n = 1$

$$f(w_1) = a + d$$

$$f(w_2) = a$$

$$f(v_0) = a + 2d$$

$$f(u_0) = a + 5d$$

$$f(v_1) = a + 3d$$

$$f(u_1) = a + 4d$$

Case (ii): when $n = 2$

$$f(w_1) = a + d$$

$$f(w_2) = a$$

$$f(v_0) = a + 2d$$

$$f(u_0) = a + 6d$$

$$f(v_1) = a + 3d$$

$$f(v_2) = a + 4d$$

$$f(u_1) = a + 5d$$

$$f(u_2) = a + 7d$$

Case (ii): when $n \geq 3$

$$f(w_1) = a + d$$

$$f(w_2) = a$$

$$f(v_0) = a + nd$$

$$f(u_0) = a + (2n + 2)d$$

$$f(v_i) = a + (i + 1)d, 1 \leq i \leq n - 2$$

$$f(v_{n-1}) = a + (n + 1)d$$

$$f(v_n) = a + (n + 2)d$$

$$f(u_i) = a + (n + 2 + i)d, 1 \leq i \leq n - 1$$

$$f(u_n) = a + (2n + 3)d$$

Table 4. Edge labels of the U -star, $n \geq 1, n \in \mathbb{N}$.

Nature of n	$n \geq 1$
$f^*(w_1v_0)$	$ (1 - n)d , n \geq 1$
$f^*(v_0u_0)$	$ (n + 2)d , n \geq 1$
$f^*(u_0w_2)$	$ (2n + 2)d , n \geq 1$
$f^*(w_1v_i)$	$ id , 1 \leq i \leq n - 2$
$f^*(w_2u_i)$	$ (n + 2 + i)d , 1 \leq i \leq n - 1$

The function f is clearly injective and also table 4 shows that $f^* : E \rightarrow \{d, 2d, 3d, 4d, \dots, nd\}$ is bijective. Hence f is arithmetic sequential graceful labeling and the U -star graph is an arithmetic sequential graceful graph.

Example 3.4.1:

The U -star graph admits arithmetic sequential graceful labeling

4 Conclusion

We showed that the Star graph, t –star, U –star, double star are arithmetic sequential graceful in this work. Analyzing arithmetic sequential graceful on other families of graphs is our future work.

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